

Full length article

Development and experimental characterization of a c-Si low concentrator photovoltaic receiver for wireless laser power transmission (WLPT) under non-uniform irradiance of 808 nm

Álvaro Valera-Albacete ^{*} ,
Eduardo F. Fernández

Advances in Photovoltaic Technology (AdPVTech), CEAECTEMA, University of Jaén (UJA), 23071 Jaén, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Wireless Laser Power Transmission
Low Concentrator Photovoltaics
Laser-PV Energy Conversion
Photovoltaics

ABSTRACT

This work presents the experimental characterization of a low concentrator photovoltaic (LCPV) receiver based on a 3×3 array of c-Si IBC solar cells for Wireless Laser Power Transmission (WLPT) using an 808 nm laser source. The receiver incorporates a crossed compound parabolic concentrator (CCPC) to enhance optical coupling under static but inherently non-uniform laser irradiance. Comprehensive optical, thermal, and electrical measurements were carried out to evaluate beam distribution, angular response, and interconnection performance. The results show that the Gaussian beam profile produces significant photocurrent variations among the cells, while voltage and fill factor remain relatively uniform. Three interconnection strategies were assessed, revealing that current-based ring grouping minimizes mismatch losses to below 3% and achieves power output comparable to the ideal independent-cell case. In contrast, series and parallel layouts suffer considerably higher losses. In addition, the CCPC provides a wide angular acceptance with high efficiency preserved for beam deviation angles up to $\pm 30^\circ$. The receiver reached power conversion efficiencies (PCE) of 15.6–16.3% at 806 nm, approaching the theoretical limit of 17.8–18.4% at the optimum wavelength (~ 955 nm). These findings demonstrate the feasibility of employing low-concentrator optics in WLPT receivers and underline the critical role of current-homogeneous grouping and tailored power management strategies to achieve efficient and reliable WLPT operation.

1. Introduction

Wireless Laser Power Transmission (WLPT), also referred to as Laser Power Transmission (LPT) or, in a broader framework, High-Power Optical Transmission (HPOT), is a far-field wireless energy transfer technology based on laser beam emission, propagation through free space, and photovoltaic reconversion at the receiver. As schematically illustrated in Fig. 1, a WLPT system is composed of two main sub-systems: an emitter and a receiver, coupled through a free-space optical transmission medium. The emitter sub-system converts the electrical input power into an optical beam by means of a laser source, supported by control electronics and beam-control units, while optical components are used to shape, collimate and direct the beam towards the receiver. After propagating through the transmission medium, the optical beam is collected by the receiver optics and converted back into electrical power by a laser photovoltaic power converter (LPC), whose output is

conditioned by control electronics before supplying the electrical load. The overall system efficiency is therefore governed by the combined performance of the emitter, the transmission channel and the receiver, making WLPT fundamentally a system-level optimisation challenge rather than a single-device problem [1]. Currently, an emerging application of WLPT include space systems, unmanned aerial and ground vehicles, underwater platforms and remote sensors, particularly in scenarios requiring contactless power delivery over long distances. Within the HPOT framework, fibre-based optical power transmission is often considered complementary to free-space WLPT, extending the applicability of optical energy transfer concepts where wireless propagation is not feasible [1,2]. A major advantage of WLPT is its high directivity and achievable power density, which enable long-distance energy delivery with compact receivers. In addition, WLPT offers intrinsic galvanic isolation, immunity to electromagnetic interference and enhanced operational safety compared to electrical cabling, making it particularly

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: avalera@ujaen.es (Á. Valera-Albacete).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlastec.2026.115299>

Received 19 January 2026; Received in revised form 16 March 2026; Accepted 10 April 2026

Available online 17 April 2026

0030-3992/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

attractive for environments where conventional power delivery is impractical, hazardous or mass-constrained [3]. Despite these benefits, the technology is still constrained by low end-to-end efficiency, which is consistently identified as the principal bottleneck for large-scale deployment. Efficiency losses arise from limited electrical-to-optical and optical-to-electrical conversion efficiencies, beam divergence and propagation losses, pointing and tracking errors, as well as thermal effects at high irradiance levels on the photovoltaic receiver. Environmental sensitivity and safety constraints further restrict operational flexibility [3,2]. The reviewed literature indicates that WLPT should be regarded as an enabling technology for niche and mission-critical applications, rather than a near-term replacement for wired power transmission. Continued progress will depend primarily on advances in laser efficiency, beam control and high-performance photovoltaic laser power converters to improve system-level efficiency and robustness.

Progress advances in laser power converters (LPCs), which constitute the dominant efficiency bottleneck at the receiver side, state-of-the-art photovoltaic laser power converters based on III-V semiconductors—predominantly GaAs and related alloys—have demonstrated conversion efficiencies exceeding 60% with a record value of 68.9% achieved under monochromatic illumination near 850–860 nm [4]. Such high efficiencies arise from precise bandgap–wavelength matching, high internal radiative efficiency, advanced photon management strategies (including back reflectors and photon recycling), and careful mitigation of series resistance losses. LPCs are typically fabricated analogous to those used in high-concentration photovoltaic cells, with device active areas ranging from sub-mm² to a few mm² in order to balance thermal management, current density and optical coupling constraints. Depending on voltage and power requirements, LPCs may be implemented as single-junction devices or as monolithically series-connected architectures, which introduce additional trade-offs between efficiency, manufacturability and tolerance to non-uniform illumination.

A well-known limitation of photovoltaic (PV) systems is the occurrence of electrical mismatch, which arises when individual cells or modules connected in series or parallel exhibit non-identical current–voltage (I–V) characteristics. In series-connected strings, the operating current is constrained by the weakest cell, while in parallel configurations voltage dispersion and unequal current sharing further degrade performance. As a result, mismatch effects manifest as power losses, increased thermal stress, and, in severe cases, hot-spot formation, ultimately impacting both efficiency and long-term reliability of PV arrays [5]. These phenomena are particularly critical in advanced applications such as concentrated photovoltaics and laser-based power transmission. In WLPT systems, the photovoltaic receiver operates under irradiation conditions that are fundamentally different from conventional solar photovoltaics, making beam non-uniformity and electrical mismatch critical loss mechanisms. Laser beams typically exhibit Gaussian or distorted intensity profiles, and even small misalignments, beam divergence or optical aberrations lead to strong spatial non-uniformities on the active area of the laser power converter (LPC) [2,4]. In this specific context, mismatch occurs not only between discrete devices but also within monolithically series-connected laser power converters, where finite beam size and misalignment produce strong irradiance gradients. Modelling of multi-sector GaAs converters

demonstrates a clear trade-off between mismatch and spillage losses, with efficiency degradation becoming increasingly severe as the number of series-connected segments increases [6]. Similar conclusions are drawn for multi-junction LPCs, where current mismatch between sub-cells can be directly inferred from I to V characteristics and is strongly influenced by optical absorption and device design [7]. Moreover, temperature-dependent current matching in dual-junction GaAs LPCs introduces additional efficiency penalties, reaching up to 20% under realistic operating conditions, underscoring the need for integrated opto-electro-thermal design [8]. Early analytical studies demonstrated that even modest statistical dispersion in cell I–V characteristics can lead to significant power losses in series-connected networks, with sensitivity increasing with current mismatch and fill factor [9]. Subsequent system-level analyses showed that certain array configurations can partially suppress mismatch penalties, with reported losses below 1% for parallel strings of unequal length under realistic conditions [10]. Under non-uniform irradiance or partial shading, mismatch losses increased markedly and lead to multi-peak P–V characteristics that challenge conventional MPPT strategies, with experimentally reported string-level power losses exceeding 10% in severe cases [11]. Mismatch losses in concentrating photovoltaic systems are strongly determined by the power conversion architecture rather than by optical non-uniformity alone, as discussed in [12]. Centralized conversion schemes amplify mismatch effects by electrically coupling non-uniformly illuminated modules, whereas decentralized architectures such as string- and module-level conversion substantially reduce power losses by allowing each unit to operate closer to its own maximum power point. This architectural decoupling results in smoother power degradation under angular misalignment and improved tolerance to irradiance non-uniformity. In the context of WLPT, these findings support the interpretation of the receiver as an optical–electrical buffer, in which optical conditioning and electrical architecture jointly act to decouple beam-induced non-uniformities from the global electrical response of the system.

Alignment tolerance studies have shown that bare laser power converters exhibit extremely limited angular acceptance, typically below $\pm 2^\circ$, as even small incidence angles induce spot displacement and severe I–V curve distortion [13]. Such tolerances are incompatible with realistic WLPT conditions, where pointing errors and beam jitter are unavoidable. A commonly proposed mitigation strategy consists in deliberately oversizing the laser spot with respect to the LPC active area, which partially relaxes angular sensitivity by reducing relative spot walk-off. However, this approach inherently sacrifices optical coupling efficiency, lowers usable power density, and exacerbates thermal management challenges, making it poorly scalable for high-power applications. In contrast, the introduction of optical conditioning at the receiver level has been shown to extend the effective angular tolerance to several degrees, preserving I–V curve integrity and maximum power extraction under misalignment, and therefore constitutes a critical design requirement for practical WLPT receivers. Experimental studies by Miyamoto et al. [14] demonstrated that the use of fly-eye lens systems at the receiver level significantly enhances the alignment tolerance of WLPT receivers. By spatially homogenizing the incident laser irradiance through microlens arrays, these non-imaging optics enable stable electrical power extraction under angular misalignments on the order of \pm

Fig. 1. Diagram of Wireless Laser Power Transmission (WLPT) system, illustrating the emitter and receiver sub-systems, from input to output power [1].

5°, and up to $\sim\pm 10^\circ$ in optimized configurations, in stark contrast to the $< \pm 2^\circ$ tolerance typically observed for bare photovoltaic receivers. Although detailed I–V curve measurements were not reported, the preserved output power under misalignment indicates effective mitigation of mismatch-induced losses and stabilization of the operating point of the laser power converter, underscoring optical homogenization as a key enabler for practical WLPT receiver robustness. Another study demonstrated a WLPT system based on a collimated LED array, prioritizing alignment tolerance and robustness over peak efficiency [15]. Using a $50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ GaAs photovoltaic receiver, the system delivered approximately 0.8 W at 1 m with an electrical–electrical efficiency on the order of a few percent, while maintaining stable output under angular misalignments of several degrees. Compared to laser-based WLPT systems, where bare laser power converters typically tolerate less than $\pm 2^\circ$ due to beam walk-off and I–V curve distortion, the LED-based approach exhibited smooth power degradation under misalignment, reflecting its reduced sensitivity to irradiance non-uniformity. Recent work on adaptive optical wireless power transmission has demonstrated that active optical control can substantially enhance robustness to geometric misalignment and receiver variability. By employing a dynamically adjustable optical system based on a variable-focus lens combined with active beam steering, stable power delivery was achieved over transmission distances of up to 5 m, even under angular and lateral misalignment [16]. The adaptive control of the beam size enables continuous matching of the irradiance profile to the effective area of the photovoltaic receiver, preventing severe non-uniformity and abrupt degradation of electrical output. The reported system exhibited an optical efficiency of approximately 56%, primarily limited by aperture truncation and absorption losses in the adaptive lens, and showed a focal shift on the order of 6 mm per 10°C due to thermal effects. Recent research in optics for resonant beam charging (RBC) applications has increasingly addressed receiver alignment tolerance, a key limitation for practical deployment. The wide-FOV ball-lens retro-reflector receiver reported in [17] achieves exceptional angular tolerance in WLPT, maintaining stable operation up to $\pm 60^\circ$ and remaining functional beyond 70° . While this RBC-based architecture far exceeds the alignment tolerance of conventional receivers, the demonstrated end-to-end efficiency remains low ($\approx 1.2\%$), indicating limitations imposed by cavity losses and optical feedback. Ground demonstrations of lunar-oriented WLPT systems have shown that, even with efficient semiconductor lasers and GaAs photovoltaic receivers, system-level performance is strongly limited by irradiance non-uniformity, series mismatch and thermal effects at the receiver. Experimental results report electrical–electrical efficiencies below 15% and rapid efficiency degradation as receiver temperature exceeds 100°C under moderate power densities, highlighting that receiver-side constraints, rather than link feasibility, dominate overall system efficiency [18]. Early experimental demonstrations of laser wireless power transmission clearly reveal the extremely narrow pointing tolerances of direct laser-to-PV coupling. In an AFRL field test, even at a short range of 100 m, small misalignments led to severe non-uniform illumination of series-connected GaAs cells, resulting in current and power losses exceeding 75% relative to expected values [19]. These results highlight that acceptable efficiency can only be maintained through precise beam pointing and active tracking, particularly as transmission distance increases and beam wander further exacerbates spatial mismatch.

Many optical design principles developed for concentrating photovoltaics—particularly non-imaging optics and secondary homogenization stages—are directly applicable to WLPT receivers, where irradiance uniformity and angular tolerance are critical to mitigate electrical mismatch and thermal stress in laser power converters [20]. Optical elements such as beam-shaping optics, homogenisers, compound non-imaging concentrators and fly-eye lens systems, play a critical role in mitigating the fundamental limitations imposed by irradiance non-uniformity in WLPT systems. By redistributing the incident laser power over the active area of the photovoltaic receiver, these optical

components can simultaneously reduce electrical mismatch and spillage losses while relaxing alignment tolerances, thereby enabling LPCs to operate closer to their intrinsic efficiency limits when integrated into practical receiver modules. Among the available optical solutions, low-concentration optics are especially attractive for WLPT receivers, as they offer a favourable trade-off between optical efficiency, acceptance angle and system robustness [21]. Non-imaging concentrators such as cross compound parabolic concentrators (CCPCs) can increase the effective collection area and angular tolerance without requiring precise tracking, making them well suited to dynamic or long-distance laser transmission scenarios [22]. Recent studies demonstrate that CCPC-based receivers significantly improve tolerance to beam divergence, incidence angle variations and lateral misalignment, leading to measurable enhancements in electrical output under realistic operating conditions [23]. Their use in WLPT receivers is therefore justified not only for optical concentration, but also for mitigating irradiance non-uniformity and mismatch-induced distortions of the I–V characteristics, enabling the receiver to operate as an effective optical–electrical buffer under realistic alignment conditions. These findings highlight the necessity of receiver architectures that actively buffer optical imperfections through combined optical conditioning, electrical decoupling and thermal management. Despite the extensive literature on the characterization of individual LPCs, there is a notable lack of studies focusing on the development and optimization of multi-cell receivers. Such an analysis is fundamental; given the compact dimensions of LPCs, large cell arrays must be interconnected to accommodate varying laser beam sizes and shapes. Therefore, research focused on optimizing these electrical–optical architectures is essential to minimize mismatch-induced losses and enhance the overall power conversion efficiency of both the receiver and the global WLPT system. In this work, we build upon these insights and address the identified gap by focusing on the receiver as an optical–electrical buffer, combining optical concentrators and electrical architecture considerations to suppress mismatch-induced losses under inherently non-uniform laser irradiance.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Features of low-concentrator photovoltaic (LCPV) receiver

A prototype of the Low-Concentrator Photovoltaic (LCPV) receiver for Wireless Laser Power Transmission (WLPT) was designed, manufactured, and experimentally characterized at the Centre for Advanced Studies in Earth Science, Energy and Environment (CEACTEMA). The receiver integrates a 3×3 array of monocrystalline silicon (mono-Si) solar cells featuring interdigitated back-contact (IBC) technology, selected for their high efficiency, low series resistance, and mechanical robustness (Fig. 2A). Each device provides an active area of $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$. The concentrator optics of the receiver module are based on crossed compound parabolic concentrators (CCPCs) (Fig. 2B). CCPCs operate by redirecting incident radiation toward the cell surface through reflective or total internal reflection mechanisms, enabling high acceptance angles and stable performance under low-concentration, static operating conditions. This geometry has consistently demonstrated superior optical efficiency compared with alternative concentrator designs reported for similar applications [23]. The CCPC design was optimized by fixing the entrance aperture to 2.5 times the solar-cell area, which allows for a 60% reduction in semiconductor material. The concentrator units were fabricated from polyurethane-based polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), chosen for its high optical transmittance, favourable dielectric properties, and ease of manufacturing. To assess the optical and electrical performance of the CCPC units, current–voltage (I–V) characteristics were measured on PV cell operating with and without the concentrators under monochromatic illumination at 808 nm (1.523 W) using a Gaussian beam profile (Fig. 2C). Additionally, the spectral response of the cells without the PMMA concentrators was characterized with a Bentham® PVE300™ system (Fig. 2D). The absorption losses

Fig. 2. (A) Bare monocrystalline c-Si solar cell with interdigitated back-contact (IBC) architecture used in the LCPV module. (B) CCPC optical unit assembled onto the c-Si solar cell. (C) Electrical and optical characterization setup employed for evaluating the CCPC performance using a bare probe cell. (D) Spectral response measurement of the c-Si probe cell using the Bentham® PVE300™ system.

introduced by the polymer optics were estimated by comparing the external quantum efficiency (EQE) of the cells with and without the CCPC assembly. A photograph of the complete LCPV module with the numbered solar cells is shown in Fig. 3. The final prototype exhibits a total frontal aperture of $104 \times 104 \text{ mm}^2$ —including the supporting frame—and a measured mass of 123 g, corresponding to an areal density of $12.3 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$. No anti-reflective coating was applied to the front surface in this first prototype configuration.

2.2. Experimental setup for LCPV receiver characterization

The indoor experimental setup used to characterize the LCPV receiver is shown in Fig. 4. The measurement system is based on a laser-to-receiver transmission architecture composed of four main subsystems: the laser source, the emitter optics, the receiver platform, and the data-acquisition unit. The light source (A) consists of a multimode high-power diode laser operating at 808 nm (CNI® MDL-XF series), equipped with a drive-power control unit capable of providing up to 10

W of optical output. The emitter-optics stage (B) includes a plano-convex collimating lens followed by a custom-built $\approx 3.5 \times$ beam expander with a 100-mm-diameter output aperture. The receiver subsystem (C) incorporates: (i) the LCPV module mounted on a precision alignment platform, and (ii) a diffuser screen positioned interchangeably for CCD-based beam-profile characterization. Finally, the electrical data-acquisition unit (D) is composed of a Keysight Technologies® B2900B™ Source-Measure Unit (SMU) connected to a laptop running custom LabVIEW® software for automated control and recording. Due to laboratory space limitations, the receiver plane was placed at a fixed distance of 3.5 m from the emitter. Prior to the system-level characterization, the spectral profile of the laser diode was measured using a StellarNet® BLACK-Comet-SR spectrometer. Regarding the optical assembly of the emitter subsystem, the optical layout was designed through ray-tracing simulations, based on a methodology previously introduced and experimentally validated by the research team [24], using as input the measured divergence and emission wavelength of the IR laser diode. The spatial distribution of irradiance on the receiver

Fig. 3. Picture of the LCPV receiver prototype. Left: overall view of the assembled module. Right: identification of the individual c-Si solar cells within the 3×3 array.

Fig. 4. Experimental setup used for the electro-optical characterization: A) 808-nm laser diode; B) emitter-optics stage; C) Lambertian-like surface with LCPV receiver; D) data-acquisition unit.

plane was obtained using CCD beam profiling at the 3.5 m propagation distance, similarly to previous work by the authors concerning the impact of non-uniformity on III-V multi-junction CPV cells [25]. To quantify the effective size of the incident laser beam on the receiver plane, the second-moment beam radius was calculated according to the 4σ definition specified in ISO 11146-1:2021, which provides a robust characterization of beam width for both ideal Gaussian and non-ideal intensity distributions. First, the beam centroid (x_c, y_c) is obtained from the irradiance distribution $I(x,y)$ measured on the receiver plane:

$$x_c = \frac{\iint xI(x,y)dxdy}{\iint I(x,y)dxdy}; y_c = \frac{\iint yI(x,y)dxdy}{\iint I(x,y)dxdy} \quad (1)$$

The second central moments of the distribution are then calculated as:

$$\sigma_x^2 = \frac{\iint (x - x_c)^2 I(x,y)dxdy}{\iint I(x,y)dxdy}; \sigma_y^2 = \frac{\iint (y - y_c)^2 I(x,y)dxdy}{\iint I(x,y)dxdy} \quad (2)$$

Following the 4σ criterion, the beam diameters along each axis are $D_x = 4\sigma_x$ and $D_y = 4\sigma_y$. For the measured near-circular Gaussian beam, an effective beam diameter was approximated as:

$$D_{4\sigma} = \frac{D_x + D_y}{2} \quad (3)$$

The irradiance distribution $I(x,y)$ was obtained from the measured 2D irradiance maps at the receiver plane. The spatial coordinates were derived from calibrated camera pixels converted into physical dimensions. The centroid and second-order moments were computed

numerically over the measurement area to estimate the effective beam footprint on the LCPV receiver, enabling the evaluation of the spatial overlap between the incident beam and the photovoltaic cell array. To calibrate the power density values, the 50(150)A-BB Ophir® thermal sensor was employed for total optical power measurements of the focused laser beam.. Thermal characterization of the LCPV receiver was performed using a FLUKE IR camera, assuming an emissivity of 0.95. In addition, the electrical response of each of the nine solar cells within the module was measured under different incident optical powers and angles of incidence (AOI), enabling the assessment of optical-electrical coupling and non-uniform illumination effects.

2.3. Electrical mismatch analysis

Because the LCPV module operates as an electrically interconnected array, mismatch losses become relevant. These losses arise when individual cells exhibit different I-V characteristics, causing the overall module to deviate from the ideal maximum-power-point (MPP). This situation is common in photovoltaic assemblies due to optical non-uniformity, thermal gradients, and cell-to-cell manufacturing variations. The mismatch analysis was carried out using the electrical parameters extracted from the I-V curves of each device, considering both series- and parallel-connection schemes. In a series configuration, the current of the entire string is constrained by the lowest short-circuit or operating current among the cells, which directly impacts the output power:

$$P_{grid,series} = \min(I_{m,i}) \sum_i V_{m,i} \quad (4)$$

Where I_m and V_m are the current and voltage at maximum power point of each i -solar cell, and $P_{grid,series}$ is the electric power output supplied to the load or grid interface. In contrast, for a parallel connection the operating voltage is limited by the minimum voltage-at-maximum-power of the group, resulting in the combined output defined as:

$$P_{grid,parallel} = \min(V_{m,i}) \sum_i I_{m,i} \quad (5)$$

Where $P_{grid,parallel}$ is the electric power supplied by the solar cells parallel interconnection. The ideal mismatch-free power of the assembly is given by the sum the maximum power output (P_m) of the i -solar cells:

$$P_{ideal} = \sum_i P_{m,i} \quad (6)$$

Therefore, the mismatch loss factor for any interconnection scenario is quantified using:

$$M = 1 - \frac{P_{grid}}{P_{ideal}} \quad (7)$$

Where P_{grid} is the net electrical power supplied to the load or grid interface according to the interconnection considered. These calculations enable the identification of optimal electrical grouping strategies and provide insight into the performance limitations of the LCPV module under realistic operating conditions. Another performance metric of interest is the power conversion efficiency (PCE) provided by the receiver module. By definition, it is calculated as:

$$PCE = \frac{P_{grid}}{P_{opt}} \quad (8)$$

Where P_{opt} is the optical power of the incident beam. This efficiency metric inherently accounts for all loss mechanisms occurring along the optical–electrical conversion chain, including optical losses in the concentrator and coupling optics, potential beam-spillage and misalignment effects, spectral and quantum-efficiency limitations of the photovoltaic device, series-resistance as well as thermally induced performance degradations. Therefore, PCE provides a comprehensive measure of the end-to-end performance of an WLPT receiver.

2.4. Power conversion efficiency at the optimum wavelength

To estimate the theoretical upper limit of performance for the LCPV receiver, the monochromatic power conversion efficiency at the optimum illumination wavelength was calculated following the methodology proposed by Helmers et al. [26]. This approach compares the experimentally measured efficiency at the laser wavelength used in this work with the efficiency expected when operating at the wavelength that maximizes the device spectral responsivity. Following Helmers' approximation, for high-quality silicon devices operating under moderate concentration, both open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and fill factor (FF) vary only weakly with wavelength when moving within the long-wavelength region near the material bandgap. Therefore, the relative change in monochromatic efficiency between two wavelengths can be expressed primarily as a function of responsivity:

$$\frac{PCE(\lambda_1)}{PCE(\lambda_2)} \approx \frac{SR(\lambda_1)}{SR(\lambda_2)} \quad (9)$$

Where $SR(\lambda)$ is the spectral responsivity of the cell at wavelength λ . Then, the theoretical improvement factor when moving from 808 nm to another wavelength is proportional to SR ratio. This means that a laser at the optimal wavelength (≈ 955 nm for this solar cell) could, in theory, provide $\sim 13\%$ more monochromatic efficiency than a laser at 808 nm, all other things being equal —assuming same V_{oc} and FF as a first

approximation—.

2.5. Uncertainty analysis

The analysis of measurement accuracy followed the ISO “Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement” (GUM). Instrumental limits were derived from manufacturer specifications or calibration certificates, and type-B components were modelled using rectangular distributions ($u = \Delta/\sqrt{3}$). Repeatability tests were performed to account for the intrinsic noise of the setup, while uncertainties of derived quantities were obtained through standard error-propagation formulas. Expanded uncertainties were reported using a coverage factor $k = 2$ ($\approx 95\%$ confidence). The spectrometer used for wavelength verification contributed only marginally to the total error budget: the ± 0.25 nm wavelength accuracy corresponds to a relative uncertainty of approximately 0.03% at 808 nm, making its impact negligible compared with the electrical terms.

Temperature measurements obtained with the IR camera carry an expanded uncertainty dominated by the ± 2 °C accuracy of the instrument. Even so, the thermal gradients observed across the receiver clearly exceed this margin, ensuring that the identification of hot spots and non-uniform heating patterns remains reliable. Thus, while absolute temperatures should be interpreted with caution, the spatial contrasts and power-dependent trends can be confidently used to characterise the system's thermal behaviour. Electrical parameters exhibited very small relative deviations, typically on the order of 0.1–0.3% for voltage, current, and fill factor. In contrast, efficiency showed a wider spread ($\approx 3.5\%$), mainly because its evaluation depends directly on the optical power entering the receiver, which ranged between 1 and 5 W in the experiments and carries an inherent $\pm 3\%$ accuracy from the thermal sensor 50(150)A-BB Ophir®. The efficiencies of the individual cells, which ranged from 18% to 22%, remained comfortably within the expanded uncertainty intervals obtained from the analysis. The spread predicted by uncertainty propagation was consistently lower than the variability observed experimentally, indicating that the dispersion in efficiency arises mainly from intrinsic performance differences rather than measurement limitations. Consequently, the uncertainty bounds do not obscure the underlying mismatch effects, and the reported values preserve their capacity to discriminate cell performance across all operating conditions. All uncertainty components are summarised in Table 1.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Initial characterization

The initial characterization of the laser and beam-delivery system helped clarify its stability, spectral behaviour, and beam formation. Table 2 summarizes the comparative metrics characteristics of gaussian beam. The optical source of multimode 808 nm high-power diode laser reached a maximum electrical-to-optical efficiency of 24.8%, and its

Table 1

Relative expanded uncertainty associated with the different measuring devices employed.

Instruments	Measurement	Uncertainty
Spectrometer	Wavelength	$\pm 0.03\%$
IR Temperature camera	Temperature ^a	± 2.5 °C
Source/Measure Unit	Voltage	$\pm 0.09\%$
Source/Measure Unit	Current	$\pm 0.12\%$
Thermal Sensor	Optical Power	$\pm 3.46\%$
Error propagation formula	Fill Factor ^b	$\pm 0.23\%$
Error propagation formula	Electrical Power ^b	$\pm 0.17\%$
Error propagation formula	Efficiency ^b	$\pm 3.46\%$

^a Absolute expanded uncertainty.

^b Derived expanded uncertainty.

Table 2
Comparative metrics characteristics of gaussian beam at 1 W of optical power.

Parameter	Optical Model Trace Pro	Experimental (CCD)	Relative Deviation [%]
Beam diameter $D_{4\sigma}$ [cm]	10.02	9.58	4.5
Peak irradiance [$\text{mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$]	20.3	18.3	9.9
Average irradiance [$\text{mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$]	12.7	13.9	9.5
Peak-to-average ratio (PAR) [-]	1.61	1.32	17.78
Beam ellipticity (D_x/D_y) [-]	1.009	0.977	3.1

emission remained centred at 806 ± 1 nm across all power levels. Although the spectral width broadened with increasing power—mainly due to diode self-heating—this had no significant impact on the LCPV receiver, since the silicon solar cells maintain nearly constant responsivity within the emission band. According to the manufacturer, the laser features a beam size of approximately 5×8 mm at the aperture and a full-angle divergence below 3 mrad. Based on these parameters, the beam quality factor is estimated at $M^2 \approx 15\text{--}20$, which is typical for broad-area multimode diode lasers. The optical coupling efficiency into the receiver aperture was evaluated using a thermal power sensor by comparing the optical power measured after the optical train and at the receiver plane (3.5 m distance), resulting in negligible transmission losses and an effective coupling efficiency close to unity. However, the beam-expander optics showed about 34% transmission losses, mostly due to uncoated surfaces and multiple interfaces. The resulting beam remained close to a Gaussian shape, making it suitable for comparison with the optical model. Fig. 5 shows the two-dimensional irradiance distribution measured with the CCD sensor, together with the perimeter of the LCPV active area. The beam footprint at the receiver plane was characterized using the ISO 11146 s-moment (4σ) beam diameters along the two orthogonal axes. The beam ellipticity, defined as D_x/D_y , was 0.977, indicating an almost circular beam profile. Under this condition, small angular misalignments mainly produce a lateral displacement of the beam. For example, an angular deviation of 1 mrad at a propagation distance of 3.5 m would result in a lateral shift of approximately 3.5 mm, which remains small compared with the receiver aperture dimensions and therefore has a limited impact on the overall coupling efficiency. A detailed comparison between the CCD-measured irradiance pattern and the ray-tracing predictions is presented in Fig. 6. At 1 W, the agreement between experiment and simulation is strong: the beam diameter differed by only 4.5%, peak and average irradiance by less than 10%, and the ellipticity remained nearly identical. The largest deviation appeared in the peak-to-average ratio (17.8%), which can be attributed to small differences in the fine structure of the beam that are difficult to

Fig. 6. Average X/Y profile of beam irradiance at 1 W of optical power.

capture perfectly through ray tracing. The behaviour at higher power levels revealed additional insights. As the optical power increased to 5 W, the beam expanded from 9.58 cm to about 10.4 cm. This widening is likely related to thermal lensing in the diode or the beam-expander optics: as the components heat up, their refractive indices and focal properties change slightly, causing the beam to diverge more. This effect has practical consequences, since a larger beam footprint increases the risk of spillage losses when the beam approaches the limits of the LCPV aperture. Understanding this behaviour is essential for predicting receiver performance at elevated laser powers, where thermal effects become more pronounced. Overall, the similarity between the measured and simulated beam parameters indicates that the numerical model captures the main physical trends of the system. This consistency suggests that the model can be used with confidence to evaluate how changes in laser power, alignment, or optical design might affect LCPV performance. Fig. 7 shows the infrared temperature distribution of the back-side 3×3 -c-Si IBC array under high optical-power operation. The thermal pattern closely follows the Gaussian irradiance profile of the laser source. Central cells exhibit the highest temperatures ($40\text{--}42$ °C), intermediate cells remain between 35 and 38 °C, and peripheral cells are noticeably cooler ($31\text{--}33.5$ °C). The temperature evolution of the LCPV receiver was evaluated under three incident optical-power levels (1, 3 and 5 W), as shown in Fig. 8. Both the maximum and average temperatures on the rear surface of the module were extracted from the thermographic images. Results show that the maximum measured temperature of the solar cell remains far below the maximum operating temperature recommended by the manufacturer—over 80 °C for c-Si IBC solar cells—. Although absolute temperatures remain within safe limits, the non-uniform heating has direct implications for electrical performance. Higher temperatures in the central region decrease V_{oc} locally and increase mismatch losses when the array is electrically interconnected. These results emphasize that optical non-uniformity is the primary driver of thermal gradients in the receiver and highlight the importance of optical homogenization and thermal management for future LCPV designs.

3.2. Ray-Tracing analysis of cell irradiance

The irradiance maps and corresponding line profiles presented in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 illustrate the spatial distribution of optical power over the photovoltaic receiver cells #5 and #3 respectively. Due to the radial symmetry of the LCPV module and the Gaussian nature of the incident beam, similar irradiance patterns are observed across the cells; therefore, only the central cell (#5) and a corner cell (#3) are presented as representative cases. The maps correspond to the maximum incident optical power of 5 W, representing the worst-case condition for

Fig. 5. Spatial distribution of beam irradiance at 1 W of optical power.

Fig. 7. Infrared camera measurement of the back-side temperature distribution of the LCPV receiver at maximum optical power (5 W).

Fig. 8. Average temperature as a function of optical power, with shaded regions indicating the full measurement range (min-max) and the one-standard deviation interval around the mean.

irradiance non-uniformity and potential electrical mismatch. For the inner cells (#2, #4, #5, #6, and #8), the distribution remains relatively

symmetric, with a clear intensification near the edges forming four high-intensity regions close to the cell corners. In a CCPC concentrator, reflections on the orthogonal parabolic walls redistribute the rays along the principal axes, producing a four-lobe or cross-shaped irradiance pattern. Similar results have been observed in previous related studies [23]. Although the CCPC partially smooths the Gaussian beam, residual non-uniformities remain, which may induce thermal gradients and electrical mismatch in the laser power converter. The measured irradiance provides in Fig. 9.left varies from nearly zero in low-intensity regions to peaks of approximately 1.4–1.5 W/cm². Contour map indicates average irradiance values of about 0.12 W/cm², corresponding to a peak-to-average ratio (PAR) of roughly 12–13 (Fig. 9.right). Higher values in the Y-direction profile indicate anisotropy introduced by the beam-shaping optics, although the overall distribution remains well-centered on the cell area. A different behavior is observed for the corner cells (#1, #3, #7, and #9), where strong spatial gradients appear (Fig. 10.left). Large portions of the surface receive low irradiance while localized peaks reach 1.5–1.6 W/cm². Consequently, the average irradiance decreases to approximately 60 mW/cm² by the non-illuminated zone, leading to PAR values over 26 (Fig. 10.left). This is reflected in the Y/X-direction profiles, which show several narrow peaks indicating strong spatial fluctuations in the received optical power. Despite the

Fig. 9. Light irradiance calculated using RayTracing for central PV cell #5 with CCPC (left) and selected lines profiles (right) under maximum optical power (5 W).

Fig. 10. Light irradiance calculated using RayTracing for corner PV cell #3 with CCPC (left) and selected lines profiles (right) under maximum optical power (5 W).

presence of these hotspots, the solar cell is unlikely to experience significant thermal degradation. This is because the operating conditions remain near the optimal intensity range for crystalline silicon (c-Si), typically cited as 0.1–W/cm², while higher power densities are usually handled by III–V laser power converters [8,27,28].

3.3. Current-voltage (I–V) characteristics

Fig. 11 shows the individual I–V curves of the nine c-Si IBC cells at 5 W of optical power. A significant dispersion in short-circuit current (I_{sc}) is observed, ranging from 0.07 to 0.09 A in the peripheral cells, to ~0.20 A in the intermediate ring, and up to ~0.45 A in the central cell (#5). Such a large disparity directly reflects the noteworthy non-uniformity of the irradiance profile incident on the receiver. In contrast open-voltage (V_{oc}) exhibits only minor variations across the array. Most cells fall within 0.63–0.67 V, corresponding to differences below 5%. This narrow voltage distribution aligns with the temperature gradients observed (~10 °C). Since V_{oc} depends logarithmically on light intensity but decreases nearly linearly with temperature, the limited dispersion indicates that temperature effects dominate over optical non-uniformity in determining the voltage behaviour. Thus, even under markedly different irradiance levels, the voltage remains relatively stable compared with the short-circuit current I_{sc} . Given these results, current mismatch clearly constitutes the main limitation for module-level interconnection.

Under the assumption of a static laser link with negligible pointing jitter, grouping cells with similar photocurrent—high (cell #5), medium (#2, #4, #6, #8), and low (#1, #3, #7, #9)—becomes an effective strategy to minimize mismatch losses. In this static scenario, the spatial distribution of irradiance remains stable over time, ensuring that each group consistently operates within its intended current class and enabling the interconnection to achieve near-ideal performance. From a power-management perspective, the strong current imbalance suggests that the most effective strategy is the implementation of submodule-level maximum power tracking, where each current-homogeneous group or even solar cell operates at its own maximum power point (P_m). Such distributed tracking minimizes mismatch losses caused by irradiance non-uniformity and enables a significantly higher energy yield than a single centralized Maximum Power Point Tracer (MPPT) architecture.

3.4. Optical power effects on electrical performance

Fig. 12 summarizes the evolution of V_{oc} , I_{sc} , FF , and P_m for the nine c-Si IBC cells under increasing optical power. The results confirm the strong electrical imbalance induced by the non-uniform irradiance profile. The I_{sc} shows the largest dispersion across the array: the central cell (#5) reaches ~0.45 A at 5 W, intermediate cells remain around 0.18–0.22 A, and peripheral cells stay below 0.10 A, corresponding to a relative current spread exceeding 500%. In contrast, V_{oc} varies only (0.63–0.70 V), mainly governed by temperature differences, while FF remains relatively stable in the 72–76% range. The P_m follows the same hierarchy as I_{sc} —with values of ~0.25 W, ~0.10 W, and 0.03–0.04 W for the high-, medium-, and low-irradiance groups, respectively—because P_m is strongly dictated by the I_{sc} level. This linear-like trend originates from the fundamental response of the cells: I_{sc} scales almost linearly with incident optical power because it is directly proportional to the photogeneration rate, and P_m mirrors this behaviour since voltage remains nearly constant and generated current has demonstrated to have a linear behaviour with the input light intensity. In contrast, V_{oc} increases only logarithmically with irradiance, and FF shows a similarly slow dependence, as both parameters are governed by diode physics and thermal voltage rather than by the absolute photon flux. Overall, these results indicate that current mismatch dominates the electrical behaviour of the array, whereas voltage remain comparatively uniform. Consequently, grouping cells with similar I_{sc} levels and implementing submodule-level MPPT becomes crucial to mitigate mismatch losses under the inherent non-uniform illumination conditions of the LCPV configuration.

3.5. Angle of incident effects on electrical performance

In Fig. 13, the normalized electrical parameters as a function of the

Fig. 11. Current-voltage (I–V) characteristic curves of the nine c-Si IBC solar cells in the 3 × 3 receiver array under a non-uniform Gaussian laser beam at 808 nm with 5 W optical power. Each cell has an active photovoltaic area of 2 × 2 cm².

Fig. 12. Normalized values of electrical parametner: open-circuit voltage, short-circuit current, fill factor and maximum power output, as a function of incident optical power.

angle of incidence (AOI) are presented. The results show that I_{sc} exhibits the strongest angular dependence, remaining close to unity up to $\sim 10\text{--}15^\circ$, but decreasing to 0.70–0.85 at 30° and dropping further to 0.40–0.60 at 45° , depending on cell position within the array. In contrast, V_{oc} shows only a mild decline, maintaining ≥ 0.97 of its initial value up to 30° and remaining above 0.95 even at the largest AOI. The FF remains remarkably stable across the entire range, with variations below 3%, and only at 45° do some low-irradiance cells show a slightly larger reduction. As a result, the normalized maximum power closely follows the behaviour of I_{sc} , remaining within 0.80–0.90 at 30° and decreasing to 0.45–0.60 at 45° , confirming that angular performance is primarily governed by the loss of photocurrent rather than by voltage or diode-quality degradation. At moderate angles of incidence (AOI $\approx 10\text{--}20^\circ$), several cells exhibit a clear relative enhancement of electrical performance, with normalized I_{sc} increasing by approximately 5–10% compared to normal incidence, while others remain close to unity or begin to decrease. This cell-dependent behaviour arises from the lateral displacement of the beam footprint under oblique incidence, which shifts the high-intensity region of the irradiance profile across the array. Cells located closer to the direction of beam shift intercept a larger fraction of the irradiance peak and therefore experience a local photocurrent gain, whereas cells positioned farther away suffer a corresponding reduction. Since V_{oc} varies by less than 2–3% and the fill factor remains within $\pm 2\text{--}3\%$ over the same angular range, the observed I_{sc} increase directly translates into a relative enhancement of P_m of up to 8–12% for favourably illuminated cells. At larger AOI ($\geq 30^\circ$), the beam displacement exceeds the effective collection area, leading to a simultaneous degradation of I_{sc} and P_m across all cells and the disappearance of these relative gains. This behaviour is consistent with the angle-

dependent capture efficiency trends reported in [23] and confirms that most of the angular sensitivity in the present system arises from optical coupling losses rather than from cell-level limitations. Previous studies on photovoltaic power-by-light converters show that small pointing deviations—typically on the order of only a few percent of the beam radius—already lead to significant power losses, highlighting the tight alignment constraints of direct laser-to-cell coupling systems [13]. Research on long-range laser power beaming for aerospace applications similarly identifies narrow pointing tolerances and the need for active tracking to maintain acceptable efficiency [19]. By contrast, optical receivers incorporating angular-tolerant optics, such as fly-eye or multi-element front ends, typically sustain useful operation up to incident angles of $\sim 14^\circ$ before the collected power drops sharply, unless enhanced with secondary folding mirrors to extend the acceptance range [14]. When compared with these references, the LCPV prototype demonstrates a relatively wide operational window.

3.6. Mismatch losses

Fig. 14 presents the electrical power output obtained for different interconnection architecture scenarios: Ideal (mismatch-free), Series, Parallel, and Ring. All scenarios exhibit a linear increase of electrical power with optical input, confirming that the module operates in a photocurrent-limited regime. At 1 W, the Ideal case delivers ~ 0.16 W, closely followed by the Ring configuration (~ 0.15 W). The Parallel case achieves ~ 0.13 W, while the Series case yields only ~ 0.05 W. This hierarchy persists at higher powers. A notable result is the near-overlap between the Ideal and Ring curves across all operating conditions. Despite the strong non-uniformity inherent to the Gaussian beam

Fig. 13. Normalized values of electrical parameter: open-circuit voltage, short-circuit current, fill factor and maximum power output, as a function of angle of incidence (AOI).

Fig. 14. Electrical output power of the LCPV receiver for ideal, series, parallel, and ring interconnections as a function of optical input power.

profile, the ring-type grouping—based on current homogeneity—captures almost the full extractable power of the system, with deviations typically below 3%. In contrast, the Series configuration exhibits the largest performance penalties, with electrical output reduced by more than a factor of three relative to the ideal case at high optical power. Its shallower slope in Fig. 14 suggests that mismatch becomes increasingly dominant at higher irradiance, likely due to the increasing peak-to-average ratio (PAR = 1.32) of the Gaussian beam and amplified differences in photocurrent among central and peripheral cells. The Parallel configuration performs substantially better than Series because

voltage mismatch is limited (<5%), consistent with earlier I–V observations. However, its output remains 5–10% below that of the Ring layout, indicating that simple parallelization cannot fully compensate for wide current disparities. Additional insight is provided by Fig. 15 which depicts the mismatch-loss coefficient M for each interconnection scenario (see Eq. (7)). The Series configuration shows the highest losses, with M values around 70% at 1 W and remaining above 58% at 5 W, confirming its strong sensitivity to current non-uniformity. The Parallel case exhibits moderate mismatch, decreasing from ~ 15% at 1 W to ~ 6% at 5 W, reflecting its partial compensation of current differences and the small dispersion in voltage. By contrast, the Ring configuration

Fig. 15. Mismatch losses for the series, parallel, and ring interconnection schemes under increasing optical power.

maintains mismatch losses below 3% throughout the entire operating range, with M slightly decreasing as the optical power increases—consistent with its excellent agreement with the Ideal scenario. Overall, these results show that the choice of interconnection topology is a critical design factor in LCPV receivers. While conventional series or parallel configurations amplify mismatch effects depending on their sensitivity to current or voltage disparities, ring-type grouping facilitates the isolation of current-homogeneous subsets, reducing electrical losses to near-optimal thresholds. This highlights the value of current-based grouping and submodule-level power management as effective strategies for maximizing electrical output under strongly non-uniform illumination. It must be noted, however, that these conclusions hold under the assumption of a static wireless laser power system with negligible beam-pointing jitter. In dynamic scenarios—where atmospheric turbulence, mechanical vibration, or misalignment could shift the Gaussian beam across the receiver—the ring topology may become more sensitive, as a moving hotspot would repeatedly change which cells belong to each current class, potentially inducing rapid mismatch fluctuations. Under such non-static operating conditions, more robust architectures (e.g., adaptive grouping, real-time reconfigurable interconnections, or distributed MPPT per cell or submodule) would likely be required to maintain stable performance in the presence of pointing instabilities.

3.7. Optical-to-electrical conversion efficiency at optimum wavelength

Fig. 16 presents the power conversion efficiency (PCE) of the LCPV receiver under increasing optical input power for different electrical interconnection scenarios, together with the theoretical maximum efficiency obtained from the interpolated spectral response of the c-Si IBC cells at the optimum wavelength (955 nm), following the calculations described in section 2.4. This theoretical curve accounts for both the optical efficiency of the CCPC concentrator and the intrinsic PV conversion efficiency of the solar cells, representing the upper bound achievable under ideal spectral conditions. For the measured system operating at 806 nm, the Ideal configuration achieves PCE values of 15.7% at 1 W, increasing slightly to 16.3% at 5 W. The Ring configuration closely follows the Ideal case, with deviations below 1%-absolute, confirming that current-based grouping effectively preserves conversion efficiency despite strong irradiance non-uniformity. The Parallel connection exhibits moderately lower efficiencies, from 13.4% at 1 W to 15.2% at 5 W, consistent with voltage homogenization and partial tolerance to photocurrent variation. As expected, the Series layout yields the lowest PCE, ranging from 4.6% at 1 W to 6.9% at 5 W, reflecting its strong sensitivity to current mismatch. The theoretical optimum-wavelength curve reaches 17.8–18.4% across the tested optical power levels. The comparison between optimum-wavelength and the measured

Fig. 16. Measured PCE of the LCPV receiver under different interconnection schemes (ideal, series, parallel, ring) at 806 nm, compared with the theoretical maximum PCE at the optimal wavelength of 955 nm.

Ideal case at measured 806-nm confirms that, while the LCPV receiver performs well at the operating wavelength of the laser source, additional relative gains of $\sim 10\text{--}15\%$ could be achieved by using a laser source closer to the spectral optimum of the cell—provided that V_{oc} and FF remain unchanged—. The observed increase of PCE with optical power reinforces that the system operates in a photocurrent-limited regime, where performance is governed largely by the optical coupling rather than by intrinsic cell degradation or resistive losses. Considering the uncertainty budget associated with the efficiency determination (expanded relative uncertainty $\pm 3.46\%$), all measured PCE values fall well within the expected confidence interval. In particular, the small difference between Ideal and Ring curves remains significantly below this threshold, further validating the robustness of the ring-type interconnection under static, jitter-free operation. While these results demonstrate that the LCPV receiver achieves stable and competitive conversion efficiencies at 806 nm, significantly higher optical-to-electrical efficiencies have recently been reported using III-V semiconductor devices. In particular, GaAs-based multi-junction laser power converters have achieved optical-to-electrical conversion efficiencies above 60% and output powers up to 30 W under high-power laser illumination [29]. These devices clearly outperform silicon-based receivers in terms of power density and efficiency due to their optimized bandgap and reduced thermalization losses. However, the focus of this work is not on maximizing the intrinsic conversion efficiency of the photovoltaic material. Nevertheless, the interconnection strategies investigated here are largely technology-independent and could therefore also be applied to future receivers based on high-efficiency GaAs laser power converters.

4. Conclusions

This work presented the design, fabrication, and full characterization of a 3×3 low-concentrator photovoltaic receiver operating under monochromatic laser illumination. The study shows that the overall performance of the module is primarily governed by the non-uniform distribution of irradiance across the cells, which drives significant electrical mismatch within the array.

- Optical measurements confirmed a near-Gaussian beam profile that becomes broader at higher input powers, creating observable irradiance gradients. Thermal analysis revealed only modest temperature variations, indicating that the differences in electrical behaviour arise mainly from illumination non-uniformity rather than thermal effects.
- Electrical results demonstrated that mismatch is the dominant loss mechanism, driven by strong variations in short-circuit current among cells, while voltage and fill factor remain comparatively stable.
- Evaluating different interconnection schemes showed that conventional layouts are highly sensitive to this mismatch, whereas grouping cells by photocurrent—implemented through the ring topology—substantially improves performance and brings the module response close to ideal conditions.
- The implementation of CCPC optics significantly expands the receiver's collection area—reducing the amount of semiconductor material required—while maintaining high conversion efficiency for beam deviation angles up to $\pm 30^\circ$. This wide angular acceptance is essential for practical WLPT deployments, as it provides the necessary tolerance to tracking inaccuracies and beam misalignment, ensuring robust performance even with high-efficiency semiconductor materials.
- Finally, the measured power-conversion efficiency of the best configurations closely approached the theoretical potential expected under optimized spectral conditions, highlighting both the robustness of the proposed receiver architecture and the opportunities for improvement through better spectral matching of the laser source.

Overall, the results demonstrate that effective current-balancing strategies and tailored interconnection schemes are essential for achieving high-efficiency laser-powered photovoltaic reception under realistic irradiation conditions. In particular, when employing high-efficiency semiconductor devices the incorporation of dedicated optical elements becomes a fundamental design requirement that enable a substantial reduction of active semiconductor area while preserving high conversion efficiency and angular tolerance. These findings provide a strong and reliable foundation for the future development of compact, high-performance wireless power transmission systems. Future work should address beam-jitter conditions, adaptive or reconfigurable interconnection approaches, and wavelength-optimized laser sources to further exploit the full potential of III-V photovoltaic technologies in dynamic or long-range applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Álvaro Valera-Albacete: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Elvira Castillo-García:** Validation, Software. **Florencia Almonacid:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Eduardo F. Fernández:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work is part of the project RePowerSiC (Grant Agreement No. 101160868) founded by European Union through the EIC Pathfinder Challenge program.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

[1] P. Sanmartín, E. F. Fernández, A. García-Loureiro, y F. Almonacid, «High-power optical photovoltaic transmission: towards a new paradigm», *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 223, p. 116031, nov. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2025.116031.

[2] Y. Zheng, et al., «Wireless laser power transmission: recent progress and future challenges», *Space Sol. Power Wirel. Transm. Jun.* vol. 1, n.o 1 (2024) 17–26, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sspwt.2023.12.001>.

[3] K. Jin y W. Zhou, «Wireless Laser Power Transmission: A Review of Recent Progress», *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 34, n.º 4, pp. 3842-3859, abr. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2018.2853156.

[4] C. Algora et al., «Beaming power: Photovoltaic laser power converters for power-by-light», *Joule*, vol. 6, n.º 2, pp. 340-368, feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.joule.2021.11.014.

[5] A. Luque López y S. Hegedus, Eds., «Fabrication Spread and Mismatch Losses», en *Handbook of photovoltaic science and engineering*, Repr., Chichester: Wiley, 2009.

[6] R. Peña y C. Algora, «Evaluation of mismatch and non-uniform illumination losses in monolithically series-connected GaAs photovoltaic converters», *Prog. Photovolt. Res. Appl.*, vol. 11, n.º 2, pp. 139-150, mar. 2003, doi: 10.1002/pip.469.

[7] A.-C. Wang, et al., «A method to analyze current mismatch in a multijunction laser power converter based on I-V measurements», *Jun, Appl. Phys. Lett.* vol. 118, n.o 23 (2021) 233902, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0048466>.

[8] S. K. Reichmuth, H. Helmers, S. P. Philipps, M. Schachtner, G. Siefer, y A. W. Bett, «On the temperature dependence of dual-junction laser power converters», *Prog. Photovolt. Res. Appl.*, vol. 25, n.º 1, pp. 67-75, ene. 2017, doi: 10.1002/pip.2814.

[9] L.L. Bucciarelli, Power loss in photovoltaic arrays due to mismatch in cell characteristics, *Sol. Energy* vol. 23, n.o 4 (1979) 277–288, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X\(79\)90121-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-092X(79)90121-X).

[10] T. S. Wurster y M. B. Schubert, «Mismatch loss in photovoltaic systems», *Sol. Energy*, vol. 105, pp. 505-511, jul. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2014.04.014.

[11] R. Kamal, M. Abdel-Salam, y M. Nayel, «Evaluation of mismatch power loss in a PV string composed of series-connected modules: Theory versus experiment», *Ain Shams Eng. J.*, vol. 16, n.º 7, p. 103422, jul. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.asej.2025.103422.

[12] Y. S. Kim y R. Winston, «Power conversion in concentrating photovoltaic systems: central, string, and micro-inverters», *Prog. Photovolt. Res. Appl.*, vol. 22, n.º 9, pp. 984-992, sep. 2014, doi: 10.1002/pip.2317.

[13] L. Wagner, A. W. Bett, y H. Helmers, «On the alignment tolerance of photovoltaic laser power converters», *Optik*, vol. 131, pp. 287-291, feb. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.ijleo.2016.11.072.

[14] Y. Tai y T. Miyamoto, «Experimental Characterization of High Tolerance to Beam Irradiation Conditions of Light Beam Power Receiving Module for Optical Wireless Power Transmission Equipped with a Fly-Eye Lens System», *Energies*, vol. 15, n.º 19, p. 7388, oct. 2022, doi: 10.3390/en15197388.

[15] M. Zhao y T. Miyamoto, «Efficient LED-Array Optical Wireless Power Transmission System for Portable Power Supply and Its Compact Modularization», *Photonics*, vol. 10, n.º 7, p. 824, jul. 2023, doi: 10.3390/Photonics10070824.

[16] M. Zhao y T. Miyamoto, «Automatic and adaptive optical wireless power transmission for IoT with dual mode of day and night charging», *Opt. Express*, vol. 33, n.º 22, p. 46599, nov. 2025, doi: 10.1364/OE.574553.

[17] S. F. A. Naqvi, N. Javed, N.-L. Nguyen, y J. Ha, «Wireless optical power transfer system incorporating a wide-field-of-view optical receiver», *Opt. Express*, vol. 32, n.º 16, p. 28779, jul. 2024, doi: 10.1364/OE.530207.

[18] H. Xu, B. Du, D. Shi, X. Huang, y X. Hou, «Laser wireless power transfer system design for lunar rover», *Space Sol. Power Wirel. Transm.*, vol. 1, n.º 2, pp. 129-135, sep. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.sspwt.2024.09.005.

[19] M. D. Smith, J. Brandhorst, y Henry W., «Support to a Wireless Power System Design», Defense Technical Information Center, Fort Belvoir, VA, dic. 2011. doi: 10.21236/ADA564824.

[20] K. Shanks, S. Senthilarasu, y T. K. Mallick, «Optics for concentrating photovoltaics: Trends, limits and opportunities for materials and design», *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 60, pp. 394-407, jul. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.01.089.

[21] A. Alamoudi et al., «Using Static Concentrator Technology to Achieve Global Energy Goals», *Sustainability*, vol. 11, n.º 11, p. 3056, may 2019, doi: 10.3390/su11113056.

[22] R. Winston, J.C. Miñano, Y.P. Benítez, «NONIMAGING OPTICAL SYSTEMS», en *Nonimaging Optics*, Elsevier (2005) 43–68, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-012759751-5/50004-X>.

[23] M. Xian-long, H. Yi-chao, L. Bei, Z. Pu, C. Felipe Aristizabal, Lopez, Y.L. Cun-liang, Improvements of PV receiver in laser wireless power transmission by non-imaging optics, *Sol. Energy* 255 (May 2023) 157–170, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2023.03.016>.

[24] J. P. Ferrer-Rodríguez, E. F. Fernández, H. Baig, F. Almonacid, T. Mallick, y P. Pérez-Higueras, «Development, indoor characterisation and comparison to optical modelling of four Fresnel-based high-CPV units equipped with refractive secondary optics», *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 186, pp. 273-283, nov. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2018.06.050.

[25] J. M. Saura, P. M. Rodrigo, F. M. Almonacid, D. Chemisana, y E. F. Fernández, «Experimental characterisation of irradiance and spectral non-uniformity and its impact on multi-junction solar cells: Refractive vs. reflective optics», *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 225, p. 111061, jun. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2021.111061.

[26] H. Helmers et al., «68.9% Efficient GaAs-Based Photonic Power Conversion Enabled by Photon Recycling and Optical Resonance», *Phys. Status Solidi RRL – Rapid Res. Lett.*, vol. 15, n.º 7, p. 2100113, jul. 2021, doi: 10.1002/pssr.202100113.

[27] J. T. Howell, M. J. O'Neill, y R. L. Fork, «Advanced Receiver/Converter Experiments for Laser Wireless Power Transmission», presentado en Solar Power from Space - SPS 2004, dic. 2004, p. 187. Accedido: 14 de marzo de 2026. [En línea]. Disponible en: <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2004ESASP.567..187H>.

[28] M. Xian-long, L. Bei, C. F. A. Lopez, y L. Cun-liang, «Multi-field coupling characteristics of photovoltaic cell under non-uniform laser beam irradiance», *Sustain. Energy Technol. Assess.*, vol. 52, p. 101963, ago. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.seta.2022.101963.

[29] S. Fafard y D. Masson, «Vertical Multi-Junction Laser Power Converters with 61% Efficiency at 30 W Output Power and with Tolerance to Beam Non-Uniformity, Partial Illumination, and Beam Displacement», *Photonics*, vol. 10, n.º 8, p. 940, ago. 2023, doi: 10.3390/Photonics10080940.